

COMMON CHILD VIOLATIONS ENCOUNTERED BY PUPILS IN SCHOOL: BASIS FOR SCHOOL-BASED POLICY MAKING

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 3

Pages: 403-412

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2063

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12776472

Manuscript Accepted: 05-17-2024

Common Child Violations Encountered by Pupils in School: Basis for School-Based Policy Making

Jean P. Pamocino*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to determine and compare the common child violation encountered by pupils in school. This study covered the two hundred thirty-two (232) Grade IV to VI pupils of Asia Elementary. This study was descriptive and comparative in nature. It utilized frequency distribution, percentage, weighted mean, and one-way ANOVA in its treatment of statistical data. The study utilized a researcher-made instrument that determine the extent of child violations encountered by the pupils. The following are the salient findings of the study: majority of the research respondents were 10-11 years old, female and in Grade IV. Emotional, verbal, and physical violations were at “moderate extent” with 2.04, 1.98 and 1.96 respectively. Violations encountered from schoolmates (2.58) and classmates (2.54) were at “moderate extent” while “very low extent” from teachers (1.59) and school head (1.21). When grouped by profile, significant differences were found in sex and grade level. On the extent of violations encountered from schoolmates, classmates, teachers, and school head when were grouped according to their profile, significant differences were found in sex and grade level. The results gave insights to the formulation of school-based policy focusing on gender sensitivity.

Keywords: *common, child violations, verbal, physical, emotional, schoolmates*

Introduction

Violence against children (VAC) is a crucial global problem that every country in the world faces and tries to end. This violence come in varied forms and generally include neglect; physical, verbal, sexual, and emotional or psychological abuse; maltreatment and exploitation; and cruelty and discrimination. Both boys and girls are vulnerable to violence, especially younger children. Violence against children can happen anywhere at home, in school, communities, and online. As a matter of fact, violence affects all children regardless of ethnicity or socio-economic status.

Child violations whether physical, verbal, or sexual – usually results in low self-esteem, fear, anger, and helplessness among children. In many Third World countries, child violations against children continues to be a pressing problem. Such violations are often manifested in the forms of abuse. In the study conducted by the World Health

Organization (WHO, 2016), it was found out that significant numbers of children experience maltreatment, resulting in life- long consequences for victims. On the other hand, PLAN Philippines (2009) cited that the United Nations World Report on Violence against Children accounted on the violence of children in education setting. Specifically, there were occurrences of physical and psychological punishments, gender-based violence and discrimination, bullying, fighting, physical assault and gangs, homicide and physical injury, and weapons in school as violations of children’s rights.

Quality education is governed by so many factors and one of which is providing children with a friendly and conducive environment. In the article of Clapper (2010), he highlighted the importance of safe and healthy learning environment for all children. Being a teacher, it is our responsibilities to set the tone of our classroom and to make sure that our learning environment is free from any form of distractions so it can attract more learning. It is also our prime duty to protect the children under our custody from any form of abuses, violence, bullying and discrimination as these will hinder them from growing cognitively and affectively.

Though Asia Elementary School has recorded minimal complaints on child violations, the school is still steadfast in its campaign on zero tolerance policy for any of child abuse, exploitation, violence, discrimination, bullying and other forms of abuse.

This research was made to further assess the child violations prevalent in the school and who are the usual perpetrators. The result of this study will give insight in the formulation of school-based policy that will intensify and strengthen the school’s campaign on child protection.

Research Questions

The main concern of this study was to determine the most common child violations encountered by intermediate pupils of Asia Elementary School. Specifically, this research sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex ; and
 - 1.3. grade level?
2. To what extent are the violations on the following areas evident among the pupils?
 - 2.1. physical;

- 2.2. verbal; and
- 2.3. emotional?
3. What is the extent of child violations encountered by the pupils in school towards their schoolmates, classmates, teachers, and school heads, and as a whole?
4. Is there a significant difference on the extent of child violations encountered by the pupils in school when they are grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant difference on the extent of child violations encountered by the pupils in school towards their schoolmates, classmates, teachers, and school heads when they are grouped according to their profile?

Literature Review

The primary function of the school is to provide learning environment for students to learn and acquire knowledge and skills. It is supposed to be a haven for children where they are free to exercise and explore their potentials to the fullest. However, in the present time, the school has been considered as a place where violence often takes place and that the need for Child Protection Policy in schools is demand (UNICEF, 2017).

The school is next to the family which serves as a platform that offers a remarkable experience in the development of a child. According to Shehzadi (2017), the school is the best place of self- grooming and to identify their hidden abilities and skills. The moment a child goes to school; there are new opportunities for his intellectual and social development. Applebury (2021), emphasized the importance of safe and learning environment for students of all ages. Without it the learning will not be effective. Furthermore, when violence is part of the educational setting, all students are affected in some way. In fact, Lussier and Fitzpatrick (2016), argued that high schoolers who feel less safe at school have decreased learning potential and more emotional problems. That is why teachers and other school personnel possess greater responsibility in making the school environment secure and safe for everybody. Additionally, they must be equipped with knowledge and expertise in handling child protection issues in the school. In school, the school authorities and teachers are the foremost persons to provide school children with all the protection they need. Their role in the loco- parentis doctrine empowers them to act in the place of parents.

Article 218 of the Family Code also recognizes the important roles and responsibilities that administrators, teachers, academic and non-academic personnel play in the execution of this duty. Furthermore, Article XIV, Section 3, of the 1987 Constitution emphasizes the need for all educational institutions to instill the value of patriotism, nationalism, and respect for all humanity. This would only mean that teachers, administrators and other school personnel shall perform their duties and responsibilities in the school in accordance to what the law is stipulating.

The 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) establishes the right of the child to education, and a view to achieving this right progressively and based on equal opportunity. Therefore, it is mandated that all appropriate measures pertaining to school discipline should be administered in a manner consistent with the child's human dignity, and in conformity with the CRC.

However, despite all these mandates, cases on discrimination, bullying and exploitation affecting children are still prevalent. In the school, children often experienced different violations which may include, physical, emotional, and verbal. International Save the Children Alliance (2003) defines physical abuse/violation as a kind of violation which involves the use of violent physical force so as to cause actual or likely physical injury or suffering (e.g. hitting, shaking, spanking, kicking, or throwing the child, pinching or pulling their hair; forcing a child to stay in uncomfortable or undignified positions, or gender is often related to abuse. In fact, more boys than girls reported being victims of abuse, while abuse is not depended on the school grade, or the teacher's gender. World Health Organization (2002) linked child violence on the child's age and sex.

Violation of children's rights is punishable by law because of its effect to children's well-being. According to Gilbert et. al., (2009), he revealed in his study that maltreated children have lower educational achievement than other groups of children. Teachers being the second parent of these children, utmost care, understanding and love towards them shall be manifested. 7

To ensure that school children are protected, DepEd Order No. 40 series of 2012 otherwise knowns as the DepEd Child Protection Policy were enacted and fully implemented in every school around the country. With this department order, teachers became very careful in dealing and disciplining pupils ensuring that their rights are well-protected.

Child protection policy is a commitment to protect children from any kind of abuse by adopting certain procedures like safe recruitment, guidance, and reporting actual or suspected abuse cases (Al-Qaysi, 2018). DepEd Child Protection Policy is designed and implemented to provide the framework and guidelines for the protection of children in school from violence, exploitation, discrimination, and other forms of abuse (DepEd Order No. 40 s. 2012). This policy has been the department's answer to put an end in the ever-increasing number of children who are seriously threatened because of their vulnerabilities. This policy should be intensified to really ensure the children's welfare inside the school premises. The children are the main reason why schools or other tutelage exist. Therefore, it is the school's main duty to prioritize the welfare of its clientele. The intensified adherence to this policy warrants a violence-free school environment and highly performing learners.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive- comparative research design. This is a design where the researcher considers two variables (not manipulated) and establishes a formal procedure to compare and conclude that one is better than the other if significant difference exists.

Participants

The participants were the two hundred thirty-two (232) randomly selected grades IV to VI pupils enrolled in Asia Elementary School. Random sampling was used to establish common purpose and that was to give each of the target population an equal chance to be selected.

Instruments

In this study the researcher utilized the researcher-made instrument that determines the common child violations encountered by intermediate pupils.

Part I of the questionnaire contained the demographic details of the participants such as age, sex, and grade level.

Part II determines the common violations encountered by pupils which were also divided into three (3) aspects; physical, verbal, and emotional. Each aspect is thoroughly explained by giving several examples and was being translated in vernacular for easy understanding on the participants' part.

Responses range from "Never" to "Always". Higher scores indicate higher extent of child violations being encountered.

To answer the questionnaire, the participants were asked to put a check (/) mark on the appropriate column that would corresponds to their answer. With the assumption that the participants have little experience in answering research instrument, the researcher carefully guiding each of the participants in answering every item in the instrument and even made a bigger model of instrument using "tarpapel" to provide the participants a bigger view of every question.

Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher by browsing through the internet found the different examples of child violations categorized in various aspects.

However, knowing that the participants were all minors, the researcher decided to just focus on the top three (3) prevalent aspects; physical, emotional, and verbal.

The items covered in the instruments were validated by three (3) experts on the field. Two of them were the school's experts as far as Child Protection is concerned; the school principal and the school guidance/ CPP coordinator and the other one was the MSWD (Municipal Social Works and Development) chairperson.

The validators suggested to shorten some of the items to avoid confusions from the participants. The content validated researcher-made instrument was pilot tested among one hundred (100) non-sample grades IV to VI pupils.

Upon retrieval and checking of the questionnaires, it revealed a reliability of 0.798 using the Cronbach's Alpha. The reliability results indicated high correlations among responses. Hence, there is a strong internal consistency within and across items.

Before the final administration, the researcher sought the approval from the school principal and consent from parents or guardians. Upon approval of the school principal and parents, the researcher made some arrangements from grades IV to VI class advisers as to the time where she can give the questionnaires to the participants. Raw data was then encoded using MS Excel and SPSS software which were subject to appropriate statistical tools.

The following are the statistical tools used for analysis:

Frequency Distribution: This is utilized to place every variable in its respective category.

Percentage: The percentage is determined by dividing the part by the whole multiplied by 100. This is used in presenting the profile of the participants.

Weighted Mean: This is used to determine the extent of common violations encountered by the participants.

Standard Deviation: It is utilized to support the weighted mean and to see the homogeneity and heterogeneity of data.

T-test: T-test for independent samples set at 0.05 level of significance is used to determine if there is a difference in the participants' profile and the extent of violations encountered towards their schoolmates, classmates, teachers, and school head when they are grouped according to sex.

One-Way ANOVA: The One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is used to determine the significance of the differences on the extent of child violations encountered by the pupils towards their schoolmates, classmates, teachers, and school heads when they are grouped according to age and grade level.

Ethical Considerations

Permission letter was sent to the school principal to inform her of the objectives of the study. Also, letters of Informed Consent were sent to parents or guardians of the participants to inform them of the purpose of the study. It was emphasized to them that the result of the study will not affect their grades. This was to eliminate pressure among the participants also to ensure their honest and maximum participation in the study. Lastly, the parents and the participants were assured that data gathered will be handled with utmost confidentiality and will be used solely as basis for the improvement of the existing school policies.

Results and Discussion

The data gathered from the study are presented, analyzed, and interpreted in this chapter. The discussions are organized in parts according to the statement of the problem. The first part is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and their grade level. The second part is the extent of Child Violations encountered by the students from their schoolmates, classmates, teachers, and school administrator.

Profile of the Participants

Table 1. Profile of the Participants N= 232

Profile	Frequency	%
1.1 Age		
9 and below	6	28.9
10-11	133	57.3
12-13	28	12.1
14-16	4	1.7
Total	232	100
1.2 Male		
Male	109	47
Female	123	53
Total	232	100
1.3 Grade Level		
IV	82	35.3
V	74	31.9
VI	76	32.8
Total	232	100

Shown in Table 1 is the personal profile of the participants in terms of age, sex, and grade level. It can be gleaned from the table that in terms of age, pupils who were 10-11 years old comprised the biggest percentage with 133 or 57.3%. Another bigger group comprising of 28.9% were pupils who were 9-10 years old. Followed by pupils who were 12-13 years old with 12.1%. Ages 14-16 registered to be the lowest in the group with 4 or 1.7%.

The findings could be interpreted as to mean that majority of the respondents in this study were within 10-11 years old. In the article written by Morin (2019), children who are ten (10) years old are on the cusp of adolescence and have the language skills and cognitive ability to gather information and formulate well-organized opinion and thoughts. Moreover, many 10-year-old children can be pleasant company at dinner and at social gatherings, capable of expressing their thoughts on current events, books music, art, and other subjects.

With regards to their sex, data show that female pupils comprising 123 or 53% was the biggest group and this was followed by male pupils with 109 or 47% of the total population. It is apparent that the population of female respondents have the higher frequency compared to their male counterparts.

Furthermore, as regards to the participants' grade level, the data showed that majority are Grade IV with 82 or 35.3%, followed by Grade VI with 76 or 32.8%. Grade V with 72 or 31.9 revealed to be the lowest in the group. Summing up, majority of the research participants belong to Grade IV.

Extent of Child Violations Evident Among the Pupils

Table 2 shows the extent of child violations encountered by pupils. When taken separately, and as a whole. Emotional violations ranked first with the mean score of 2.04 followed by physical violation with mean score of 1.96 and were both rated under "moderate extent".

On the other hand, verbal violations ranked the lowest in group with the mean score of 1.98 and which is rated under "low extent". Synthesizing the results, the extent of child violations is revealed to be under "moderate extent" as indicated by the mean score of 1.98.

Munro (2001) considered emotional abuse as the most common form of abuse. Likewise, the New Zealand-based non-profit group Women’s Refuge said that psychological or emotional abuse is the most common type of violence experienced by women and children and it is deemed by many as the “worst kind of abuse”.

Table 2. *Extent of Child Violations Encountered by the Pupils*

Extent of Violation	Mean Score	SD	Interpretation
As a Whole	1.98	0.60	Encountered at a Moderate Extent
Emotional	2.04	0.68	Encountered at a Moderate Extent
Physical	1.96	0.64	Encountered at a Moderate Extent
Verbal	1.94	0.75	Encountered at a Moderate Extent

Note: 4.21-5.00 – Very High; 3.61-4.20 – High; 2.41-3.60 – Moderate; 1.81-2.40 – Low; 1.00-1.80 – Very Low

Extent of Child Violations Encountered by Pupils towards their Schoolmates, Classmates, Teachers, and School Head, and as a Whole

Table 3. *Extent of Child Violations encountered from Schoolmates, Classmates, Teachers, and School Head*

Extent of Violation encountered	Mean Score	SD	Interpretation
Schoolmates	2.58	0.87	Encountered at a Moderate Extent
Classmates	2.54	0.90	Encountered at a Moderate Extent
Teachers	1.59	0.88	Encountered at Very Low Extent
School Head	1.21	0.59	Encountered at Very Low Extent
As a Whole	1.98	0.60	Encountered at Low Extent

Note: 4.21-5.00 – Very High; 3.61-4.20 – High; 2.41-3.60 – Moderate; 1.81-2.40 – Low; 1.00-1.80 – Very Low

Table 3 posits the child violations encountered by the pupils from schoolmates, classmates, teachers, school head and as a whole. In terms of violations encountered by pupils from their schoolmates and classmates, both fall under “moderate extent” category as indicated by their mean scores of 2.58 and 2.54 respectively. This data indicate that schoolmates and classmates are the usual culprit in child violations.

On the other hand, violations encountered from teachers and school heads revealed to be under the “very low extent” category as indicated by mean scores of 1.59 and 1.21 respectively. School administrator’s results ranked as the lowest knowing that learners are not directly handled by them.

Summing up, the extent of child violations encountered by pupils among schoolmates, classmates, teachers, and school head when taken as a whole was found to be under “low extent” as indicated by the mean score of 1.98. The data further signify that the school is still a safe place for all learners.

Difference on the Extent of Child Violations Encountered by the pupils in school when they are grouped according to their profile

Table 4.1. *Difference on the Extent of Child Violations Encountered by the pupils in school when they are grouped according to Age*

Age	Mean Score	SD	F	p-value	Sig	Decision
9 below	2.03	.66	1.130	.338	Not Significant	Accept Ho
10-11	1.92	.59				
12-13	2.12	.443				
14-16	2.08	.773				

Results in the f-test in table 4 reveal that the extent of child violations encountered by pupils in school when they were grouped according to age was not significantly different as indicated by its computed results where $f = (1.130)$; $p = 0.338$, $p < 0.5$. The results may imply that children of the same age level are less likely to maltreat his peers.

Table 4.2 presents the difference on the extent of child violations encountered by the pupils in school when they are grouped according to sex. Results in the t- test revealed that when pupils were grouped according to age, no significant difference was noted as indicated by its computed results where $t = (6.105)$; $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.5$. The data further indicate that pupils usually encountered violations because of their sex or gender.

Table 4.2. *Difference on the Extent of Child Violations Encountered by the pupils in school when they are grouped according to Sex*

Sex	Mean Score	SD	t	p-value	Sig	Decision
Male	2.22	.59	6.105	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Female	1.77	.53				

In the article written by Nahla Mansour Al-Ali and Khulood K. Shattnawi (2018), they pointed out that gender of students is one of the reasons that students get bullied, and female students are more likely of being harassed by their peer. More so, Theoklitou et.al (2012) divulged that gender is often related to abuse. In fact, more boys than girls reported being victims of abuse, while abuse is not depended on the school grade, or the teacher's gender. World Health Organization (2002) linked child violence on the child's age and sex.

Table 4.3. *Difference on the Extent of Child Violations Encountered by the pupils in school when*

Grade Level	Mean Score	SD	F	p-value	Sig	Decision
IV	2.11	.68	3.536	.031	Significant	Reject Ho
V	1.86	.58				
VI	1.96	.50				

Table 4.3 posits the difference on the extent of child violations encountered by the pupils in school when they are grouped according to grade level. Results in the f-test revealed that when pupils were grouped according to grade level, a significant difference was noted as indicated by its computed results where $f = (3.536)$; $p = 0.031$, $p < 0.5$. The data further indicate that the pupil's grade level is another factor in child violations. However, this was contradicted by the study of Theoklitou et.al (2012) who stressed out that child violations are not dependent and associated with the child's grade level.

Difference on the Extent of Child Violations Encountered by the pupils in school towards their schoolmates, classmates, teachers and school heads when they are grouped according to their profile

Table 5.1. *ANOVA and T-test Results on the Extent of Child Violations encountered by pupils towards their Schoolmates*

Age	Mean Score	SD	F	p-value	Sig	Decision
9 below	2.53	.91	1.743	.159	Not Significant	Accept Ho
10-11	2.54	.88				
12-13	2.93	.60				
14-16	2.67	1.05				

Sex	Mean Score	SD	t	p-value	Sig	Decision
Male	2.84	.81	4.371	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Female	2.36	.85				

Grade Level	Mean Score	SD	F	p-value	Sig	Decision
IV	2.61	.88	.232	.793	Not Significant	Accept Ho
V	2.53	.96				
VI	2.61	.75				

As to the schoolmates, the f-test results on age and grade level showed no significant differences as to the extent of child violations encountered by the participants as shown by the computed f-value $(1.743) = (.159)$, $(.232) = (.159)$, respectively, $p < .05$. This implies that as to schoolmates, age and grade level were not considered as risk factors in child violations, therefore accept the null hypothesis. On the other hand, t-value on sex revealed to have significant difference as shown by the computed t-value $(4.371) = .000$, $p < .05$. The

data further imply that sex or gender plays a dominant element of child violations.

Table 5.2. ANOVA and T-test Results on the Extent of Child Violations encountered by pupils towards their Classmates

Age	Mean Score	SD	F	p-value	Sig	Decision
9 below	2.60	1.09				
10-11	2.44	.83	1.600	.190	Not Significant	Accept Ho
12-13	2.81	.64				
14-16	2.75	1.10				
Sex	Mean Score	SD	t	p-value	Sig	Decision
Male	2.83	.79	4.839	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Female	2.28	.91				
Grade Level	Mean Score	SD	F	p-value	Sig	Decision
IV	2.61	.104				
V	2.42	.83	.960	.384	Significant	Accept Ho
VI	2.57	.78				

Table 5.1 display the ANOVA and T- test Results on the Extent of Child Violations encountered by pupils towards their Classmates. Based on the results, age and grade level do not differ significantly as far as extent of child violations was concerned. Furthermore, for age the f-test value is $(1.600) = .190$ and for the grade level, the f-test value $(.960) = .384$, $p < .05$. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected. The results indicate that the pupils are often violated because of their sex or gender. Andrews, et al (2008) argued that sex is often associated with abuse since in his study he found that girls are more likely to be victims of certain forms of maltreatment than boys.

Table 5.3. ANOVA and T-test Results on the Extent of Child Violations encountered by pupils towards their Teachers

Age	Mean Score	SD	F	p-value	Sig	Decision
9 below	1.75	.98				
10-11	1.53	.84	1.199	.311	Not Significant	Accept Ho
12-13	1.51	.75				
14-16	1.92	1.26				
Sex	Mean Score	SD	t	p-value	Sig	Decision
Male	1.89	1.02	4.993	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Female	1.34	.64				
Grade Level	Mean Score	SD	F	p-value	Sig	Decision
IV	1.89	1.08				
V	1.38	.69	8.026	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
VI	1.48	.71				

With regards to teachers, the ANOVA computation reveals no significant difference on grade level as shown in the computed f-value $(1.199) = .311$. However, significant differences were found on sex $(t=4.993)$ and grade level $(f=8.026)$. With this, null hypothesis shall be accepted. This data suggest that teachers are likely to commit violations on children based on their sex and grade level.

Table 5.4. ANOVA and T-test Results on the Extent of Child Violations encountered by pupils towards their School Head

Age	Mean Score	SD	F	p-value	Sig	Decision
9 below	1.26	.69	.447	.720	Not Significant	Accept Ho
10-11	1.18	.56				
12-13	1.21	.51				
14-16	1.00	.00				

Sex	Mean Score	SD	t	p-value	Sig	Decision
Male	1.32	.76	2.911	.004	Significant	Reject Ho
Female	1.10	.35				

Grade Level	Mean Score	SD	F	p-value	Sig	Decision
IV	1.33	.80	3.096	.047	Significant	Reject Ho
V	1.10	.36				
VI	1.18	.46				

Table 5.4 revealed the ANOVA and T-test results on the extent of child violations encountered towards the school head. Generally, the age was found to have no significant difference as indicated by its t-value (.447) = .720, $p > .05$. This would mean that children of different ages were treated equally by the school head. On the other hand, the t-test results on sex and f-test results on grade level showed significant differences as to the extent of child violations encountered by the participants from the school head as shown by its computed t and f-values (2.911) = .004, (3.096) = .047, respectively, $p < 0.5$. These data imply that school heads often commit violations to children based on their sex and grade level.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher can conclude that the school is not a safe place anymore for children. Everybody knows that all schools around the country are guarded with so many rules and policies in favor of children however, violations on their rights are still prevailing. Probably because of the nature, upbringing, and environment the child has exposed with.

In this study, violations do not occur when children are grouped according to same age bracket and grade level. As we all knew that younger children are much prone to violations made or inflicted by those older than them. Same is true with the grade level, the lower the grade level is the higher the chance of being bullied or violated.

On the other hand, sex is always a dominant element in violations. Males and females always contradict as to who are more prone and less prone to any kind of violations. Oftentimes, teachers are branded as the main culprit in this what so called violation. However, in this study it came out that it's not directly the teacher instead it is their schoolmates and classmates who are hurting pupils physically, emotionally, and verbally.

Violations done by schoolmates and classmates is a serious problem for those bullied pupils because every day they can see them, and the acts will become habitual and repetitive.

Consequently, violations done by teachers is not a serious problem for pupils perhaps this is because of the Department Order No. 40 s. 2012 otherwise known as the Child Protection Policy. This is only a manifestation that the school is intensifying its campaign on the zero-tolerance for any act of child exploitation, violence, discrimination, and other forms of abuse.

In general, whatever violation/abuse it is, may it be physical, emotional, and verbal violation it doesn't change the fact that they are all destructive to everyone. It may harm someone's social reputation, psychological/emotional being and may even cause death. It is important to spread awareness and to take part in any activities or undertakings that would put an end or stop child violations in school, home and in community as a whole.

In the light of the findings and conclusions that have been drawn, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

For the pupils, it is essential that they are not afraid to report cases of bullying or other similar acts to authorities. They should be oriented about their rights and privileges, ensuring they also understand their corresponding responsibilities. Pupils must respect each

other regardless of individual differences, show courtesy, and maintain harmonious relationships among schoolmates, classmates, teachers, school administrators, and community members. They should always seek what is right and good in everything they do and say.

For the teachers and school administrators, it is crucial to establish good and harmonious relationships with pupils, parents, co-teachers, stakeholders, and the community. They must work together to uphold the protection and rights of every pupil, preventing problems and abuses in school and the community. Proper orientation and thorough training on child protection policy and the rights of the child are necessary. Teachers and administrators should provide pupils with wholesome educational materials, supervise their activities, protect them from harmful influences, and prevent habits detrimental to their health, studies, and morals. They should design programs and activities for pupils, parents, and stakeholders to advocate anti-bullying concepts and their roles and responsibilities, promote positive and non-violent discipline methods, and take steps to prevent bullying while ensuring appropriate interventions and counseling for victims. Emphasizing the teaching of the ESP (Edukasyon Sa Pagpapakatao) subject is vital as it serves as a guiding principle for children. School policies and regulations should be posted inside classrooms and around the school.

For parents and guardians, supervising their children and inculcating good values while highlighting the importance of good relationships among people is paramount. They should monitor their child's activities, whereabouts, and friends, and find time to talk about their daily activities, accomplishments, and any awards received. Parents should also communicate with their child's teacher adviser to stay informed about their classroom behavior. Applying positive and non-violent discipline at home, and actively participating in school activities or events that raise awareness on children's rights, positive discipline, and bullying prevention, are crucial responsibilities for parents.

For stakeholders, supporting and cooperating with the school's programs, projects, and activities, especially the Anti-Bullying Campaign, is essential. Stakeholders should be strong partners in realizing and implementing the school's projects and programs.

For the DepEd, it is important to continue training teachers on current strategies and techniques for dealing with behavioral problems and resolving conflicts. Providing interventions to help reduce bullying cases in schools is vital. School administrators, district supervisors, and division personnel should be readily available to provide technical assistance to teachers, boosting their confidence in teaching despite the challenges of conflict-related issues. **Plans for Dissemination and Advocacy**

This study focuses on the common child violations encountered by pupils in the intermediate level. The result of this study will serve as basis for school-based policy making. Moreover, the result of the study will be presented during the In-Service Training for Teacher on May 2020. The findings will also be presented to all school research coordinators and school heads during quarterly district research coordinators meeting and during staff meeting.

The crafted school-based policy will become the school's best practice in pursuing and achieving the outstanding child-friendly school. Conducting research must be included as one of the priority targets of teachers in crafting of RPMS.

Furthermore, the result of this study will also be published and disseminated in School's Publication and District Bulletin Boards and in during LAC Session and school meeting to further motivate and boost fellow teachers to also conduct action research.

References

Adam, M. (2008). Changes in early admissions: good or bad? *The Hispanic Outlook in Higher Education*, 18, 14-15. Retrieved 2017 from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/219222072?accountid=34542>.

Child Abuse Prevention Programme (CAPP) (2013). *Stay safety best practices in child protection-guide for school*. Bridge house, Cherry Orchard Hospital Dublin 10.

Clapper, T. (2010): *Creating safe learning environment*: Retrieved from: http://www.researchgate.net/publication/257835881_creating_the_safe_learning_environment/link/59e0e051aca2724cbfd6b8d1/download

Coohey, C., Renner, L. M., Hua, L., Zhang, Y. J., & Whitney, S. D. (2011). Academic achievement despite child maltreatment: A longitudinal study. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 35(9), 688-699.

DO 40, s. 2012: DepEd child protection policy. Retrieved from: <https://goo.gl/x8nMe>:November 10, 2017.

Federico, M., Jackson, A., & Black, C. (2008). Understanding the impact of abuse and neglect on children and young people referred to a therapeutic program. *Journal of Family Studies*, 14, 342-361.

- Ferrara, P., Franceschini, G., Villani, A. et al. (2019): Physical, psychological and social impact of school violence on children. *Italian Journal of Pediatrics*: Vol. 45, 75(2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13052-019-0669-z>
- Garcia, L.E. & Thornton, O. 2014. The enduring Importance of parental involvement. <http://Neatoday.org/2014/11/18/the-enduring-importance-of-parental-involvement2/>. Date of access: 13 March 2018.
- Grady, J. (2003). Stop Verbal Abuse. Houston: Therepia Publishing maltreatment 1: Burden and consequences of child maltreatment in high-income countries. *The lancet*. 2009;373:68–81.
- Gilbert, R., Widom, C.S., Browne, K., Fergusson, D., Webb, E., & Janson, S. (2009). Child maltreatment 1: Burden and consequences of child maltreatment in high-income countries. *The Lancet*, vol. 373, pp. 6881.
- Jaffee, S.R., & Maikovich-Fong, A.K. (2011). Effects of chronic maltreatment and maltreatment timing on children's behavior and cognitive abilities. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry* 52(2), 184-194.
- Jones, S. E, Axelrad, R., & Wattigney, W. A. (2007). Healthy and safe school environment, part II, physical school environment: Results from the school health policies and programs study 2006. *The Journal of School Health*, 77(8), 544-56. Retrieved 2017 from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/215673771?accountid=34542>.
- Kaur, J., & Kumar, M. (2012). The impact of the type of school and school environment on the self-concept of adolescents. *Journal of Psychosocial Research*, 7(1), 43-51. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1027215841?accountid=34542>.
- Martinez-Torteya, C., Bogat, G. A., Eye, A. V., & Levendosky, A. A. (2009). Resilience among children exposed to domestic violence: The role of risk and protective factors. *Child Development*, 80(2), 562-577.
- Mills, A. J. and Runte, M. (2004). Paying the Toll: A Feminist post-structural critique of the discourse bridging work and family,' *culture and organization*, 10(3): 237-249
- Morin, A. (2019): 10-year-old child development milestones: Your child's growth and development at age 10: Retrieved from: <http://www.verywellfamily.com/10-year-old-developmental-milestones-620710>
- Munro, K. (2001): Emotional abuse: The most common form of abuse: Retrieved: from:<http://www.verywellfamily.com/10-year-old-developmental-milestones-620710>
- Munro, K. (2001): Emotional abuse: The most common form of abuse: Retrieved from: <http://kalimunro.com/wp/articles-info/sexual-emotional-abuse/emotional-abuse-themost-common-form-of-abuse>.
- Nahla Mansaur Al-Ali and Khulood K. shattanawi (2018): Bullying in school: Reviewed: February 20, 2018. Published: March 21, 2018: DOI:10.5772/interopen.75729
- PLAN Philippines (2009). Toward a child-friendly education environment. A baseline study on violence against children in public schools
- Sapungan, G.M. & Sapungan, R. M. 2014. Parental Involvement in Child's Education: Importance, Barriers and Benefits. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences and Education*, 3(2): 42-48.
- Tuazon, A. P. (2016). School practices in parental involvement, its expected results and barriers in public secondary schools: *International Journal of Educational Science and Research*, 6(1):69-78.
- Theoklitou et al. (2012): Physical and emotional abuse of primary school children by teachers UNICEF Report 2013 UNICEF. (2009). *Child-Friendly Schools Manual*. Retrieved from https://www.unicef.org/publications/files/Child_Friendly_Schools_Manual_EN_040809.pdf.
- World Health Organization. (1999). Report of the Consultation on Child Abuse Prevention.
- UNICEF Annual Report (2014): Retrieved from: https://www.unicef.org/publications/index_82455.html
- US Department of Health and Human Services (2013): Retrieved from <https://learning.nspcc.org.uk/child-abuse-and-neglect/physical-abuse/> <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/violence-against-children> International
- Save the Children Alliance (2003): Save the Children's Policy on: Protecting Children from Sexual Abuse and Exploitation
- Vardigan, B. (2009). Verbal abuse of children. Retrieved 20/3, 2009, from <http://www.ahealthyme.com/topic/printview>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jean P. Pamocino

Asia Elementary School

Department of Education – Philippines